

TEACHERS' BURNOUT AND JOB PERFORMANCE: INPUTS FOR A TEACHERS' TEACHING CAMP

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ABSTRACT

Teacher burnout and its implications for job performance are critical concerns in the education sector. This study adopted a quantitative-descriptive design to examine the relationship between burnout and job performance among public elementary school teachers in Catbalogan City during the 2023-2024 school year. Findings revealed moderate burnout levels, primarily attributed to emotional exhaustion and depersonalization. Teacher characteristics such as gender, attitude, and work environment influenced burnout levels. While teacher performance was generally high, factors like civil status, class type, and location impacted it. A weak negative correlation between burnout and performance was observed. Recommendations include addressing burnout through stress management, workload reduction, and social support initiatives; offering counseling, mentorship, and professional development; and creating supportive work environments. Enhancing teacher performance requires equitable workload distribution, targeted support, and professional development opportunities. The study underscores the need for comprehensive interventions to address teacher well-being and effectiveness.

Keywords: *Teacher Burnout, Job Performance, Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization, Personal Accomplishment, Public Elementary School Teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a rewarding yet demanding profession due to the long hours of work and extensive workload. The teachers become burnt out as a result of the long hours of

work and extensive workload. Hence, they are prone to the risk of being physically, mentally, emotionally, and psychologically unwell. Teaching has become even more difficult in recent years because of increased paperwork and misbehaving students in class. Teachers consequently have a lot on their minds that require their complete focus, such as motivating unmotivated students and dealing with disruptive students. Therefore, the teachers' continuous exposure to a variety of job demands could lead to burnout, which might eventually give rise to less engagement at work and lower productivity.

Burnout is a psychological stress syndrome that occurs when a person is in a state of high emotional engagement for an extended period of time. It is characterized as persistent and profound tiredness with cognitive, emotional, physical, and social symptoms brought on by long-term job stress, particularly in occupations entailing a great deal of responsibility for other people and continuous interpersonal interactions. Burnout in teachers occurs when there is an imbalance between unreasonable demands and available resources. Teachers who are burnt out on their jobs struggle to achieve and constantly address shortcomings. Therefore, the teaching and learning processes are both at risk when a teacher is burnt out. As they supervise student projects, assess their performance, and plan classes, teachers frequently find that their workweek is significantly extended. Given the length of time spent working and the demands of teaching, burnout may eventually become incapacitating (Safari, 2020).

Consequently, an increased degree of burnout becomes very common among teachers. Across the globe, the teachers' mental well-being appears to be in a worse state in recent times. The 2017 Educator Quality of Work Life Survey by the American Federation of Teachers found that 61 percent of teachers in the United States said their employment were sometimes stressful, and 58 percent blamed the stress on their poor mental health, which frequently resulted in burnout. A 2021 Gallup survey showed that the rate of burnout among K-12 teachers in the United States is higher than the professionals in any other industry. Similarly, a 2021 Education Support study found that more than 70 percent of teachers in the United Kingdom reported declining mental health and feelings of heightened stress due to their work that resulted to increased levels of burnout (Smith, 2022).

In Asia, with a teaching staff of over 1.6 million, China has one of the largest teacher populations in the world and one of the worst rates of burnout. According to 2019 meta-analyses conducted, Chinese teachers ranked second among their counterparts in 35 other nations in terms of emotional exhaustion. Additionally, the poll found that about 30 percent of Chinese teachers had major burnout, which is 10 percent more than that of teachers in the United States. The same survey also revealed that Chinese cultural context, social and educational conditions shape a unique burnout profile of Chinese teachers (Han et al., 2023).

The Philippine education system is not invincible to teacher feelings of burnout before, during, and after the COVID-19 pandemic. The teachers' burnout was addressed by the Alliance of Concerned Teachers (ACT) Philippines as a severe welfare issue that

undermines their abilities, health, and morale. More than 70 percent teachers of public schools who participated in an online survey conducted during the first half of the School Year 2020-2021 said that their workload had a negative impact on their physical and mental health, with 10 percent of them admitting that they were already getting sick because of issues with their demanding responsibilities (Hernando-Malipot, 2021).

Furthermore, the eight-hour work restriction is also frequently breached by teachers, with about 41 percent of those in Metro Manila and 29 percent of those outside of Metro Manila working nine to 16 hours or more on school days. These teachers also work extra hours, which deprives them of their due proportionate vacation compensation after a school year with a maximum of 220 instructional days. For instance, without receiving a single day of leave benefits, the teachers worked 297 days in the School Year 2020–2021 between June 1 and July 10, 2021.

The global phenomenon of burnt-out teachers is detrimental to the quality of education of a country. The global learning crisis is actually a teaching crisis and, thus, the quality of teachers has the greatest impact on improving student learning outcomes. The teachers are responsible for planning lessons, organizing activities in class, developing curriculum, supervising classes, maintaining student discipline, providing cover for teacher shortages, administering timetables of tasks, and evaluating and assessing students' performance. Most developing countries in Asia and the Pacific, such as the Philippines, face major challenges in recruiting the best candidates for a long-term teaching career. On this matter, developing effective teachers during their careers is the key to driving learning outcomes (Panth & Tulivouri, 2021).

The performance of the teachers' jobs must therefore be of utmost concern to those involved in education. All actions that employees take while at work or as quantifiable actions, behaviors, and outputs that are either directly or indirectly generated by employees towards achieving organizational goals are referred to as job performance. It may also be described as the anticipated total amount of behavioral episodes that the employee exhibits over the course of a certain period. Additionally, it refers to how well an employee can do the job using organizational resources under normal circumstances. A teacher's performance on the job is specifically defined as their contribution to the accomplishment of educational goals. It applies to all places where students are present, not only the classroom or the school. It is viewed as a multifaceted construct that comprises, among other things, lesson planning, instruction, student evaluation, commitment, and efficient monitoring (Limon & Sezgin-Nartgun, 2020).

The Philippine educational system sets the minimum qualification standards for teachers in response to the challenge to provide high-quality education to the students. The National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS) has been institutionalized and implemented through the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Memorandum Order Number 52, Series of 2007, and the Department of Education (DepEd) Order Number 32, Series of 2009 as program reform thrusts to improve teacher quality. With the implementation of the K-12 Program, teaching quality requirements are also making remarkable shift to focus on high-quality teachers who

are equipped with appropriate competences and are better prepared to assume their roles and functions. Subsequently, the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) was sought to heed the challenge of the need for high-quality K-12 teachers along well-defined domains on professional learning, competent practice, and effective management (DepEd, 2017).

At present, the overwhelming challenge to uphold higher teacher quality in the K-12 Program has made the DepEd align the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) with PPST, with different assessment instruments for Teachers I to III and for Master Teachers I to IV. Each of the assessment tools describes the duties and responsibilities of teachers across career stages, Key Result Areas (KRAs) for the realization of those duties, and the specific objectives are clearly defined. Also, it provides in detail the various means of verification (MOV) that serves as proof of the attainment of the specific objectives alongside the performance indicators, from outstanding to poor performance (DepEd, 2018).

Despite the program reform thrusts on improving teacher quality, a Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM) reported inadequate teacher preparation programs, low-quality students enrolled in teacher preparation programs, and scant opportunities for professional development as reasons for the teachers' poor teaching performance. The results of the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) between 2014 and 2019 reflected and demonstrated that teacher quality was a problem. During these years, the elementary LET results revealed an average passing percentage of 28 percent, and the secondary LET results revealed an average passing rate of 36 percent. Based on the Public Education Expenditure Tracking and Quantitative Service Delivery Study (PETS-QSDS) by the World Bank Philippines, it was revealed that elementary and high school teachers are ill-equipped to teach significant portions of the K-12 curricula. In addition, this survey revealed that, with the exception of elementary English teachers, the average elementary or high school teacher could only accurately respond to less than 50 percent of the questions on subject content examinations (Philippine News Agency, 2020).

Although there has been an increase in interest in studying the relationship between teacher burnout and work performance, the effects of these variables on one another have been assessed in various contexts. Consequently, it is crucial to conduct research that will evaluate how burnout that teachers may experience impacts on their job performance in a local context, such as in the cases of public elementary school teachers in the Schools Division of Catbalogan City, where there has been known but unreported cases of teacher burnout that contributed to some teachers' personal and professional breakdown. For instance, a teacher in a public secondary school experienced a mental breakdown that ultimately led in resigning from teaching and transitioning to an administrative position. Another public secondary school teacher who had fallen into a state of mental breakdown had been confined in a medical institution where prompt psychological assistance was given. These occurrences implied that burnout may be an indirect cause of teachers' breakdowns. Hence, this study will focus on providing a local data on how the teachers' burnout could impact on their job

performance.

Research Questions

This study determined the relationship between the burnout and job performance of public elementary school teachers in the Schools Division of Catbalogan City, during the School Year 2023-2024, as inputs for a teaching camp. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of the following variates:
 - 1.1 age and sex;
 - 1.2 civil status;
 - 1.3 gross monthly family income;
 - 1.4 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5 number of years in teaching;
 - 1.6 grade level taught;
 - 1.7 type of class taught;
 - 1.8 location of teaching assignment;
 - 1.9 relevant in-service trainings and;
 - 1.10 attitude toward the teaching profession?
2. What is the burnout level of the teacher-respondents based on the following dimensions of the Maslach Burnout Inventory-Educators Survey (MBI-ES) by Maslach and Jackson (Davaribina & Asl, 2021):
 - 2.1 emotional exhaustion;
 - 2.2 depersonalization; and
 - 2.3 personal accomplishment?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the burnout level of the teacher-respondents along the three mentioned aspects and each of their profile variates?
4. What is the job performance of teacher-respondents based on their rating in the Results-Based Performance Management System (Tool) for teachers?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the job performance of teacher-respondents and some of the identified variates:
 - 5.1 teacher-related variates; and
 - 5.2 burnout level?
6. What intervention program may be proposed based on the findings of this study?

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in the different public elementary schools in the ten districts of the Schools Division of Catbalogan City. These schools include: Catbalogan I Central Elementary School (CES), Socorro Elementary School (ES), and Totoringon ES in District I; Catbalogan II CES, Salug ES, Lobo ES, Cawayan ES, and San Andres ES in District II; Catbalogan III CES, Libas ES, Caramayon ES, and Lagundi ES in District III,

Catbalogan IV CES, San Vicente ES, Cagutian ES, and Albalate ES in District IV; Catbalogan V CES, Pupua ES, Jose P. Casino ES, and Manguihay ES in District V; Bliss CES, New Mahayag ES, and Cagudalo ES in District VI; Guinsorongan ES, Palanyogon ES, Bunuanan ES, and Bangon ES in District VII.

Figure 1
 The Map Showing the Locale of the Study

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a quantitative–descriptive research design to determine the relationship between burnout and job performance of public elementary school teachers in the Schools Division of Catbalogan City during School Year 2023–2024. Data were gathered from 150 teachers using total enumeration through a validated questionnaire and an observation checklist. The questionnaire collected data on teachers' profiles, attitude toward the teaching profession, and burnout level based on the Maslach Burnout Inventory–Educators Survey, while job performance was obtained from the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS-PPST) ratings. Permission to conduct the study was secured from concerned DepEd authorities, and data were collected through survey administration and classroom observation following ethical standards of confidentiality and anonymity. The collected data were tabulated and analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency count, percentage, mean, weighted mean, median, median absolute deviation, and standard deviation, as well as inferential statistics including Spearman's rank correlation coefficient and Fisher's t-test at a 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results revealed that the teacher-respondents were predominantly young, female, married, and in the early to mid-career stage, with most pursuing or having completed graduate studies. Teachers generally exhibited a positive attitude toward the teaching profession and demonstrated very satisfactory to outstanding job performance based on RPMS-IPCRF ratings. However, the findings showed a moderate level of burnout among teachers across the dimensions of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. Several profile variables—particularly sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, type of class taught, location of teaching assignment, and attitude toward the teaching profession—were significantly related to burnout dimensions, while fewer variables were significantly related to job performance. Moreover, a statistically significant but weak negative relationship was found between job performance and burnout, indicating that higher performance tended to be associated with lower burnout levels, although the relationship was not strong.

Conclusions

The study concluded that while public elementary school teachers in the Schools Division of Catbalogan City generally perform at a high level and maintain a positive outlook toward their profession, they nonetheless experience moderate burnout that warrants attention. Burnout among teachers is influenced more by personal attitudes and work-related conditions than by age, income, teaching experience, or training attendance. Emotional exhaustion and depersonalization emerged as critical concerns, particularly among female teachers and those assigned to challenging teaching contexts. Although job performance remained high, it did not fully protect teachers from burnout, underscoring the complex and multifaceted nature of teacher well-being and the need for

comprehensive support beyond performance-based measures.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, it is recommended that school administrators and education authorities implement targeted interventions to reduce teacher burnout, including stress management programs, counseling services, mentoring, and workload redistribution. Support systems should be strengthened, particularly for teachers in challenging assignments and underserved locations, and gender-sensitive policies should be promoted. Professional development initiatives should focus not only on instructional competence but also on mental health and well-being. Additionally, performance evaluation should be used as a developmental tool rather than solely for accountability. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct longitudinal and qualitative studies to further explore the causes of teacher burnout and to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions aimed at sustaining both teacher performance and well-being.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in full compliance with established ethical standards in educational research. Prior approval to conduct the study was obtained from the concerned authorities of the Department of Education, including the Schools Division Superintendent, district supervisors, and school heads. Participation of the teacher-respondents was purely voluntary, and informed consent was secured prior to data collection. The respondents were clearly informed of the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and their right to decline or withdraw at any stage without any negative consequences. Anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were strictly upheld, and all collected data were treated as privileged information and used solely for academic and research purposes. Access to RPMS-PPST records was undertaken with proper authorization and in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. All data were securely stored and reported in aggregate form to prevent identification of individual participants, ensuring respect, integrity, and protection of the respondents throughout the research process.

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